

FREQUENCY OF VARIOUS SUBTYPES OF BRONCHIECTASIS AT MUFTI MEHMOOD MEMORIAL TEACHING HOSPITAL (MMMTH), D.I. KHAN

Dr Shah Zaib Khan^{*1}, Dr Sunila Aslam², Dr Muhammad Junaid Usman³, Farista Gull⁴,
 Zakia Marwat⁵

^{*1}Post Graduate Resident Internal Medicine DHQ MTI Dera Ismail Khan

²Consultant Gynecologist at City Hospital Lakki Marwat

³Post Graduate Resident, Medical Teaching Institution Mardan Medical Complex Mardan

⁴Student DPT

⁵M Phill Scholar

¹shahzaibkhandoctor@gmail.com, ²drsunilaaslam@gmail.com, ³junaidmarwat1999@gmail.com,

⁴drfarishtagull5555@gmail.com, ⁵zakiamarwat666@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20082342>

Keywords

Bronchiectasis; High-resolution computed tomography; Radiological subtypes; Cylindrical bronchiectasis; Pakistan

Article History

Received: 10th Dec 2024

Accepted: 15th Feb 2025

Published: 1st March 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Dr Shah Zaib Khan

Abstract

Background

Bronchiectasis is a chronic respiratory disease characterized by irreversible airway dilatation and recurrent infections. High-resolution computed tomography (HRCT) plays a pivotal role in diagnosis and allows radiological classification into distinct subtypes, which may reflect disease severity and chronicity. Data regarding the distribution of bronchiectasis subtypes in Pakistan, particularly from southern Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, are limited.

Objective

To determine the frequency of various radiological subtypes of bronchiectasis among adult patients presenting to Mufti Mehmood Memorial Teaching Hospital (MMMTH), Dera Ismail Khan.

Methods

This descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted in the medical unit of MMMTH over a six-month period from July 2024 to Dec 2024. Adult patients (18–70 years) with HRCT-confirmed bronchiectasis were consecutively enrolled. Radiological subtypes were classified according to the Reid classification into cylindrical, varicose, cystic (saccular), and mixed types. Demographic and clinical data were recorded. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 25. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize variables, and chi-square tests were applied to assess associations between bronchiectasis subtypes and selected demographic factors. A p-value ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

A total of 101 patients were included, comprising 61 males (60.4%) and 40 females (39.6%), with a mean age of 44.35 ± 15.62 years. Cylindrical bronchiectasis was the most common radiological subtype, observed in 51 patients (50.5%), followed by cystic bronchiectasis in 30 patients (29.7%). Mixed and varicose subtypes were each identified in 10 patients (9.9%). No statistically significant associations were found between bronchiectasis subtypes and gender (p

= 0.134), age group ($p = 0.139$), smoking status ($p = 0.564$), or place of residence ($p = 0.273$).

Conclusion

Cylindrical bronchiectasis is the predominant radiological subtype among patients presenting with bronchiectasis at a tertiary care hospital in southern Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. The lack of significant associations with demographic and clinical variables underscores the heterogeneous nature of the disease. Standardized HRCT-based radiological subtyping is essential for improved disease characterization and may support better clinical decision-making in resource-limited settings.

INTRODUCTION

Bronchiectasis is a chronic and progressive respiratory disorder characterized by irreversible dilatation of the bronchi and bronchioles, resulting in impaired mucociliary clearance, persistent airway inflammation, and recurrent respiratory infections. Clinically, patients commonly present with chronic productive cough, purulent sputum, and recurrent lower respiratory tract infections, leading to substantial morbidity, frequent hospitalizations, and a marked reduction in quality of life. Although bronchiectasis was historically considered an orphan disease, recent epidemiological data demonstrate a rising global prevalence, particularly among aging populations and in regions with a high burden of chronic respiratory infections.[1-3]

The etiology of bronchiectasis is heterogeneous and varies significantly across geographic regions. Post-infectious causes remain the most common worldwide, while chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), asthma, connective tissue disorders, and immunodeficiency states are also recognized contributors[4]. In many Asian and South Asian populations, post-tuberculosis (TB) sequelae have emerged as a dominant underlying cause, reflecting the persistent burden of pulmonary TB in these regions[5,6]. This marked regional variation underscores the need for locally generated data to better understand disease patterns and to inform context-specific diagnostic and management strategies.

High-resolution computed tomography (HRCT) of the chest is the diagnostic modality of choice for bronchiectasis, allowing detailed visualization of airway morphology and associated parenchymal abnormalities. Based on HRCT findings,

bronchiectasis is commonly classified according to the Reid classification into cylindrical, varicose, cystic, and mixed subtypes[7-9]. Cylindrical bronchiectasis is characterized by uniform bronchial dilatation with loss of normal tapering, varicose bronchiectasis exhibits irregular or beaded airway contours, while cystic bronchiectasis represents the most severe form with saccular dilatations and a honeycombing appearance. Mixed bronchiectasis demonstrates overlapping features of more than one subtype. In addition, traction bronchiectasis may be observed secondary to fibrotic lung disease; however, primary non-traction bronchiectasis remains the focus of radiological phenotyping in most clinical settings. Radiological subtyping is clinically relevant, as it reflects disease severity, chronicity, and may influence prognosis and therapeutic decision-making.

Several international studies have evaluated the distribution of bronchiectasis subtypes using HRCT. Large cohort analyses have reported cylindrical bronchiectasis as the most frequent subtype, followed by cystic and varicose forms[10,11]. In patients with coexisting COPD, the prevalence of bronchiectasis is notably higher, with cylindrical patterns predominating[11]. However, the reported distribution of radiological subtypes varies considerably across studies, likely due to differences in underlying etiologies, population characteristics, imaging protocols, and regional disease burden.

Despite the growing recognition of bronchiectasis as an important cause of chronic respiratory morbidity, data regarding the frequency and distribution of its radiological subtypes in Pakistan

remain limited. In particular, there is a paucity of institution-based studies from southern Khyber Pakhtunkhwa that systematically describe bronchiectasis patterns using standardized HRCT classification systems. Addressing this knowledge gap is essential for improving regional disease characterization, supporting radiological reporting practices, and contributing to the development of locally relevant clinical strategies.

Therefore, this study was designed to determine the frequency of various subtypes of bronchiectasis, as identified on high-resolution computed tomography using the Reid classification, among adult patients presenting to Mufti Mehmood Memorial Teaching Hospital (MMMTH), Dera Ismail Khan.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design and Setting

This hospital-based descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted in the Medical Unit of Mufti Mehmood Memorial Teaching Hospital (MMMTH), Dera Ismail Khan, Pakistan. MMMTH is a tertiary care teaching hospital serving the population of southern Khyber Pakhtunkhwa and adjacent regions. The study was carried out from July 2024 to Dec 2024 following approval from the Institutional Ethical Review Committee.

Study Population

Adult patients presenting to the outpatient and inpatient departments of the medical unit with clinical features suggestive of bronchiectasis were screened for eligibility.

Sampling Technique and Sample Size

A non-probability consecutive sampling technique was employed, whereby all eligible patients meeting the inclusion criteria during the study period were enrolled.

The sample size was calculated using the WHO sample size calculator (version 2.0). A prevalence of 7.3% for the varicose subtype of bronchiectasis, representing the least common subtype reported in previous literature, was used to ensure adequate representation. With a 95% confidence interval

and a margin of error of 5%, the calculated sample size was 101 patients.

Eligibility Criteria

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients aged 18 to 70 years
- Both male and female patients
- Patients with a confirmed diagnosis of bronchiectasis based on clinical assessment and HRCT findings
- Patients who provided written informed consent to participate

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with bronchiectasis secondary to cystic fibrosis, primary ciliary dyskinesia, or known immunodeficiency disorders
 - Patients with primary diagnoses of other chronic respiratory diseases unrelated to bronchiectasis, including interstitial lung disease, pulmonary fibrosis, or lung malignancy
 - Patients presenting with acute respiratory tract infections at the time of HRCT imaging
 - Patients with incomplete or poor-quality HRCT scans that precluded accurate radiological assessment
 - Patients with a history of major lung surgery (e.g., lobectomy or pneumonectomy) that could alter bronchial anatomy
- These exclusions were applied to minimize confounding and ensure accurate radiological classification.

Diagnostic Criteria for Bronchiectasis

Bronchiectasis was diagnosed based on a combination of clinical features, relevant medical history, and characteristic HRCT findings. Clinical criteria included chronic cough persisting for months to years, with or without purulent sputum production, and a history of recurrent respiratory infections, COPD, or asthma. Radiological diagnosis on HRCT was established by the presence of one or more of the following features: increased pulmonary markings, tram-track appearance, signet ring sign, honeycombing, or a bronchial diameter exceeding 1.5 times that of the adjacent pulmonary artery. Patients

fulfilling both clinical and radiological criteria were included in the study.

Radiological Classification of Bronchiectasis

Bronchiectasis subtypes were classified according to the Reid classification system based on HRCT findings:

- **Cylindrical bronchiectasis:** Uniform bronchial dilatation with parallel tram-track appearance or signet ring sign.
- **Varicose bronchiectasis:** Irregular or beaded bronchi with alternating areas of dilatation and constriction.
- **Cystic (saccular) bronchiectasis:** Large saccular or cystic dilatations with a honeycomb appearance, distinguished from emphysematous bullae by thicker walls and associated proximal airway abnormalities.
- **Mixed bronchiectasis:** Presence of more than one radiological subtype in the same patient. Traction bronchiectasis, typically associated with fibrotic lung disease, was acknowledged during image review; however, cases in which traction bronchiectasis represented the predominant pattern were excluded to maintain focus on primary non-traction bronchiectasis.

Data Collection Procedure

After obtaining ethical approval, eligible patients were recruited from the outpatient and inpatient departments of the medical unit at MMMTH. Written informed consent was obtained prior to enrollment, and each participant was assigned a unique identification code to maintain confidentiality.

Demographic variables, including age, sex, and area of residence (urban or rural), were recorded. Clinical data such as duration of symptoms, history of chronic respiratory infections, presence of COPD or asthma, and smoking status were collected through structured interviews and review of medical records.

All participants underwent HRCT of the chest using standard imaging protocols. HRCT scans were independently reviewed by a consultant radiologist with experience in thoracic imaging. In cases of uncertainty, images were reviewed in consensus with a second senior radiologist to

ensure diagnostic accuracy. Radiological findings were documented, and each patient was classified into the appropriate bronchiectasis subtype using the Reid classification.

Study Variables

The primary outcome variable was the radiological subtype of bronchiectasis (cylindrical, varicose, cystic, or mixed). Explanatory variables included age, sex, area of residence, duration of symptoms, smoking status, and presence of comorbid conditions such as COPD or asthma.

Data Management and Statistical Analysis

Data were entered, coded, and analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS), version 25. Quantitative variables, including age and duration of disease, were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation. Qualitative variables, such as sex, smoking status, comorbidities, and bronchiectasis subtypes, were presented as frequencies and percentages.

Stratification was performed with respect to age, sex, area of residence, and smoking status to evaluate their association with bronchiectasis subtypes. The chi-square test was used to assess associations between categorical variables, while independent sample t-tests were applied for continuous variables where appropriate. A p-value of ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was obtained from the Institutional Ethical Review Committee of Mufti Mehmood Memorial Teaching Hospital. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to data collection. Participant confidentiality and anonymity were strictly maintained throughout the study in accordance with institutional and ethical guidelines.

RESULTS

Baseline Demographic and Clinical Characteristics

A total of 101 patients with HRCT-confirmed bronchiectasis were included in the final analysis. The study population comprised 61 males (60.4%) and 40 females (39.6%), with a male

predominance. The mean age of the participants was 44.35 ± 15.62 years (range: 19–70 years). Most patients belonged to rural areas (65.3%), whereas were from urban settings.

With respect to smoking status, 49 patients (48.5%) were never smokers, were former smokers, and 25 (24.8%) were current smokers. Chronic obstructive 27 (26.7%) pulmonary

disease (COPD) was present in 51 patients (50.5%), while 18 patients (17.8%) had a history of bronchial 34.7% asthma. The mean duration of respiratory symptoms was 55.40 ± 24.58 months.

Table 1 summarizes the baseline demographic and clinical characteristics of the study population.

Table 1. Baseline demographic and clinical characteristics of patients with bronchiectasis (n = 101)

Variable	Frequency (%) / Mean \pm SD
Age (years)	44.35 ± 15.62
Gender	
• Male	61 (60.4)
• Female	40 (39.6)
Residence	
• Rural	66 (65.3)
• Urban	35 (34.7)
Smoking status	
• Never smoker	49 (48.5)
• Former smoker	27 (26.7)
• Current smoker	25 (24.8)
COPD	51 (50.5)
Asthma	18 (17.8)
Duration of symptoms (months)	55.40 ± 24.58

Frequency of Radiological Subtypes of Bronchiectasis

Based on HRCT findings using the Reid classification, cylindrical bronchiectasis was the most frequently observed subtype, identified in 51 patients (50.5%). This was followed by cystic

(saccular) bronchiectasis in 30 patients (29.7%). Mixed and varicose bronchiectasis were each observed in 10 patients (9.9%).

The distribution of radiological subtypes is presented in Table 2 and illustrated in Figure 1.

Table 2. Frequency of radiological subtypes of bronchiectasis (n = 101)

Bronchiectasis subtype	Frequency (%)
Cylindrical	51 (50.5)
Cystic (saccular)	30 (29.7)
Varicose	10 (9.9)
Mixed	10 (9.9)

Figure 1. Distribution of radiological subtypes of bronchiectasis

(Bar chart showing the relative frequencies of cylindrical, cystic, varicose, and mixed bronchiectasis subtypes based on HRCT findings.)

Figure legend: Cylindrical bronchiectasis was the predominant subtype, followed by cystic bronchiectasis, while varicose and mixed patterns were less frequently observed.

Association Between Bronchiectasis Subtypes and Demographic Variables

When stratified by gender, cylindrical bronchiectasis was more common among males (60.8%), whereas cystic bronchiectasis demonstrated a relatively balanced distribution between males (46.7%) and females (53.3%). Mixed and varicose subtypes were predominantly observed in male patients. However, the association between bronchiectasis subtype and gender was **not statistically significant** (Pearson chi-square, $p = 0.134$).

Stratification by smoking status showed that cylindrical bronchiectasis was most frequently

observed among never smokers, followed by former and current smokers. Similar distributions were noted for other subtypes. No statistically significant association was found between smoking status and bronchiectasis subtype ($p = 0.564$).

Patients were further stratified into three age groups (18–40 years, 41–60 years, and >60 years). Cylindrical bronchiectasis was most frequent in the younger age group, while varicose bronchiectasis was relatively more common in patients aged over 60 years. These differences did not reach statistical significance ($p = 0.139$).

Regarding place of residence, cylindrical and cystic bronchiectasis were more frequently observed among rural residents, while varicose bronchiectasis was equally distributed between rural and urban populations. The association between bronchiectasis subtype and residence was not statistically significant ($p = 0.273$).

Table 3 presents the stratified analysis of bronchiectasis subtypes according to selected demographic variables.

Table 3. Association between bronchiectasis subtypes and demographic variables

Variable	Cylindrical n (%)	Cystic n (%)	Varicose n (%)	Mixed n (%)	p-value
Gender					0.134
• Male	31 (60.8)	14 (46.7)	6 (60.0)	7 (70.0)	
• Female	20 (39.2)	16 (53.3)	4 (40.0)	3 (30.0)	
Smoking status					0.564
• Never	24 (47.1)	15 (50.0)	5 (50.0)	5 (50.0)	
• Former	14 (27.5)	8 (26.7)	3 (30.0)	2 (20.0)	
• Current	13 (25.5)	7 (23.3)	2 (20.0)	3 (30.0)	
Residence					0.273
• Rural	32 (62.7)	20 (66.7)	5 (50.0)	9 (90.0)	
• Urban	19 (37.3)	10 (33.3)	5 (50.0)	1 (10.0)	

Key Findings

Cylindrical bronchiectasis was the most prevalent radiological subtype in this cohort. Although variations in subtype distribution were observed across gender, age groups, smoking status, and place of residence, no statistically significant

associations were identified between bronchiectasis subtypes and these demographic or clinical variables.

DISCUSSION

This cross-sectional study provides insight into the radiological distribution of bronchiectasis subtypes among adult patients presenting to a tertiary care hospital in southern Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. The principal finding of this study was that cylindrical bronchiectasis was the most prevalent radiological subtype, accounting for approximately half of all cases, followed by cystic bronchiectasis, while varicose and mixed patterns were comparatively less frequent. These findings highlight the predominance of milder to moderate structural airway changes in our population.

The predominance of cylindrical bronchiectasis observed in this study is consistent with findings from international cohorts. Large registry-based and imaging studies from Europe and North America have similarly reported cylindrical bronchiectasis as the most common morphological pattern on HRCT, followed by cystic and varicose subtypes[12–14]. This pattern likely reflects earlier or less advanced disease in a substantial proportion of patients, as cylindrical bronchiectasis is generally considered the earliest and least severe radiological manifestation.

Comparable results have also been reported from Asian populations. Studies from Korea, Taiwan, and China have demonstrated cylindrical bronchiectasis as the dominant subtype, particularly in post-infectious and COPD-associated disease[5,10]. In TB-endemic regions, including South Asia, chronic airway damage following pulmonary tuberculosis has been identified as a major contributor to bronchiectasis, often manifesting initially as cylindrical changes before progression to more severe cystic forms[4]. The relatively high proportion of cystic bronchiectasis in our cohort may reflect delayed diagnosis and prolonged symptom duration, a common challenge in resource-limited settings.

In the present study, no statistically significant association was found between bronchiectasis subtypes and demographic variables such as gender, age group, smoking status, or place of residence. Similar findings have been reported in previous studies, where radiological morphology did not consistently correlate with demographic

characteristics[9,15]. Although male predominance was observed overall, subtype distribution did not differ significantly by sex, suggesting that disease morphology may be more closely related to underlying etiology and disease chronicity rather than demographic factors alone. Smoking status and COPD were prevalent in a substantial proportion of patients; however, no significant association was observed between smoking status and bronchiectasis subtypes. This finding aligns with prior literature indicating that while smoking and COPD are strongly associated with the presence of bronchiectasis, they do not necessarily predict a specific radiological pattern[16]. The coexistence of COPD and bronchiectasis has been increasingly recognized as a distinct clinical phenotype associated with increased symptom burden and exacerbation risk, underscoring the importance of HRCT evaluation in symptomatic patients with chronic airflow limitation[17].

Age-related variations in subtype distribution were observed descriptively, with varicose bronchiectasis appearing more frequently in older patients; however, these differences were not statistically significant. Similar age-related trends without definitive statistical associations have been reported in previous imaging-based studies[8]. This may be due to overlapping disease mechanisms and the relatively small sample size within specific subgroups.

From a clinical perspective, radiological subtyping of bronchiectasis using HRCT is important for disease characterization, assessment of severity, and potential prognostication. Cylindrical bronchiectasis is often associated with better preserved lung function, whereas cystic and varicose forms are linked to more advanced disease and recurrent infections[18]. Routine reporting of bronchiectasis subtypes may therefore assist clinicians in risk stratification and long-term management planning.

Strengths and Limitations

The strengths of this study include the use of standardized HRCT-based classification, inclusion of a well-defined adult population, and comprehensive assessment of demographic and

clinical variables. However, several limitations should be acknowledged. This was a single-center study with a relatively modest sample size, which may limit generalizability. Etiological classification of bronchiectasis was not performed, and longitudinal outcomes were not assessed. Additionally, although some contingency table cells had small expected frequencies, chi-square analysis was retained given the descriptive and exploratory nature of the study.

Future Directions

Future multicenter studies with larger sample sizes are warranted to further explore radiological phenotypes of bronchiectasis in Pakistan. Incorporation of etiological classification, microbiological data, and clinical outcomes would provide a more comprehensive understanding of disease patterns and inform region-specific management strategies.

CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates that cylindrical bronchiectasis is the most prevalent radiological subtype among adult patients presenting to a tertiary care hospital in southern Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan, followed by cystic bronchiectasis, while varicose and mixed patterns are less common. The distribution of bronchiectasis subtypes did not show significant associations with demographic factors, smoking status, or place of residence, highlighting the heterogeneous nature of the disease.

Routine HRCT-based radiological subtyping provides valuable insights into disease characterization and may aid clinicians in assessing disease severity and guiding management strategies. The findings underscore the importance of early recognition and standardized radiological reporting of bronchiectasis, particularly in TB-endemic and resource-limited settings.

REFERENCES

1. Snell N, Gibson J, Jarrold I, Quint JK. Epidemiology of bronchiectasis in the UK: Findings from the British lung foundation's 'Respiratory health of the nation' project. *Respir Med*. 2019 Oct;158:21-3.
2. Henkle E, Chan B, Curtis JR, Aksamit TR, Daley CL, Winthrop KL. Characteristics and Health-care Utilization History of Patients With Bronchiectasis in US Medicare Enrollees With Prescription Drug Plans, 2006 to 2014. *Chest*. 2018 Dec;154(6):1311-20.
3. Aksamit TR, O'Donnell AE, Barker A, Olivier KN, Winthrop KL, Daniels MLA, et al. Adult Patients With Bronchiectasis. *Chest*. 2017 May;151(5):982-92.
4. Chandrasekaran R, Mac Aogáin M, Chalmers JD, Elborn SJ, Chotirmall SH. Geographic variation in the aetiology, epidemiology and microbiology of bronchiectasis. *BMC Pulm Med*. 2018 Dec;18(1):83.
5. Yang B, Choi H, Lim JH, Park HY, Kang D, Cho J, et al. The disease burden of bronchiectasis in comparison with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease: a national database study in Korea. *Ann Transl Med*. 2019 Dec;7(23):770-770.
6. Phua HP, Lim WY, Ganesan G, Yoong J, Tan KB, Abisheganaden JA, et al. Epidemiology and economic burden of bronchiectasis requiring hospitalisation in Singapore. *ERJ Open Res*. 2021 Oct;7(4):00334-2021.
7. Juliusson G, Gudmundsson G. Diagnostic imaging in adult non-cystic fibrosis bronchiectasis. *Breathe*. 2019 Sept;15(3):190-7.
8. on behalf of the Normal Chest CT study group, Kuo W, Perez-Rovira A, Tiddens H, De Bruijne M. Airway tapering: an objective image biomarker for bronchiectasis. *Eur Radiol*. 2020 May;30(5):2703-11.
9. José RJ, Loebinger MR. Clinical and Radiological Phenotypes and Endotypes. *Semin Respir Crit Care Med*. 2021 Aug;42(04):549-55.

10. Huang HY, Chung FT, Lo CY, Lin HC, Huang YT, Yeh CH, et al. Etiology and characteristics of patients with bronchiectasis in Taiwan: a cohort study from 2002 to 2016. *BMC Pulm Med.* 2020 Dec;20(1):45.
11. Karamat A, Batool H, Anwar S, Akram S, Masood A, Rafai WA. Frequency and Pattern of Bronchiectasis in Patients with Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease Presenting in a Tertiary Care Hospital. *Proceedings.* 2021 June 26;35(3):54-7.
12. Chalmers JD, Aliberti S, Blasi F. Management of bronchiectasis in adults. *Eur Respir J.* 2015 May;45(5):1446-62.
13. Aksamit TR, O'Donnell AE, Barker A, Olivier KN, Winthrop KL, Daniels MLA, et al. Adult Patients With Bronchiectasis. *Chest.* 2017 May;151(5):982-92.
14. Chalmers JD, Mall MA, McShane PJ, Nielsen KG, Shteinberg M, Sullivan SD, et al. A systematic literature review of the clinical and socioeconomic burden of bronchiectasis. *Eur Respir Rev.* 2024 July;33(173):240049.
15. Habesoglu M, Ugurlu A, Eyuboglu F. Clinical, radiologic, and functional evaluation of 304 patients with bronchiectasis. *Ann Thorac Med.* 2011;6(3):131.
16. Yang B, Han K, Kim B, Kang HK, Kim JS, Kim EG, et al. Association between Smoking Status and Incident Non-Cystic Fibrosis Bronchiectasis in Young Adults: A Nationwide Population-Based Study. *J Pers Med.* 2022 Apr 26;12(5):691.
17. Polverino E, Goeminne PC, McDonnell MJ, Aliberti S, Marshall SE, Loebinger MR, et al. European Respiratory Society guidelines for the management of adult bronchiectasis. *Eur Respir J.* 2017 Sept;50(3):1700629.
18. Kim SH, Yang B, Yoo JY, Cho JY, Kang H, Shin YM, et al. Clinical characteristics, radiological features, and disease severity of bronchiectasis according to the spirometric pattern. *Sci Rep.* 2022 Aug 1;12(1):13167.